

Plant host range of the rice bug (RB)

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RB *Leptocoris oratorius* (Fabricius) comprises 80% of the *Leptocoris* RB collections from wetland and dryland rice in the Philippines. *L. acuta* (Thunberg) and *L. palawanensis* Ahmad also are found in significant numbers.

Only plants in the milk or dough stage are nutritionally acceptable to *L. oratorius*. It survives by being long-lived (adults can live over 3 mo) and dispersive, seeking late maturing rice or alternative grassy weed hosts. We

studied RB survival on rice and some commonly reported weed hosts.

Neonate nymphs were placed on ripening-stage rice and eight common weeds. All nymphs died on *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Paspalum conjugatum* Berg., and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv (see table).

Oryza sativa L. was the most suitable host, with the most favorable growth index, greatest fecundity, and highest number of stylet sheaths. *Echinochloa* species, led by *E. colona* (L.) Link, were acceptable hosts, but with significantly lower growth indices, fecundity, and number of stylet sheaths. Nymphal development ranged from 21 d with rice to 36 d with *Paspalum scrobiculatum* L.

Paspalidium flavidum (Retz.) A. Camus and *P. scrobiculatum* can be considered marginal hosts. □

Effect of three neem products on brown planthopper (BPH) oviposition

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We evaluated the effect of three neem products on BPH oviposition. Neem oil at 1% and 2% were prepared in water containing 1% Teepol. Neem seed kernel extract at 5% was prepared from 50 g of powdered neem seed kernel soaked in 1 liter water for 12 h, filtered, and Teepol 1% added to the filtrate. Neem cake at 5% was prepared from 50 g neem cake soaked in 1 liter water for 12 h, filtered, and Teepol 1% added to the filtrate.

Ten gravid BPH females were caged for 12 h on 40-d-old plants. Eggs were counted visually under a stereoscopic microscope. Treatments with all three neem products significantly reduced BPH oviposition (see table).

Eggs/treated plant ranged from 12 to 44, compared to 143 eggs/control plant. □

Growth and development of *L. oratorius* on rice and common ricefield grassy weeds. IRRI greenhouse, 1986.^a

Plant ^b	Growth index ^c	Insect dry weight (mg)	Fecundity (eggs/female)	Stylet sheaths (no./panicle)
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	1.9 a	18 a	65 a	1.3 a
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	1.1 b	14 ab	51 b	1.2 ab
<i>E. glabrescens</i> Monro ex Hook f.	0.9 c	12 b	41 bc	1.2 ab
<i>E. crus-galli</i> ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	0.9 c	12 b	45 c	1.2 ab
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	0.4 d	8 b	21 d	0.7 b
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i>	0.2 e	3 c	5 e	0.5 c

^aAv of 4 replications, 10 rice bugs/5 panicles. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bNymphs failed to develop on *Eleusine indica*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. ^cGrowth index = survival (%) / developmental period (d).

Effect of three neem products on BPH oviposition. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Eggs/plant ^a
Neem oil (1%)	19
Neem oil (2%)	12
Neem seed kernel extract	38
Neem cake extract	44
Control	143

^aMean of 5 replications. Means followed by common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Agronomic and economic evaluation of herbicides in transplanted rice

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In 1984, we studied the effect of five granular and two liquid herbicides and hand weeding on weed control in transplanted rice in a randomized block design with four replications. Jaya seedlings at 21 d were transplanted on 24 Jun.

Weed infestation was high. Dry weight in nonweeded control was 397

g/m² (see table). *Echinochloa colona* (L.) and *E. crus-galli* (L.) predominated (85% total dry weight). Other weeds were *Cyperus iria* (L.), *C. difformis* (L.), *Scirpus grossus* (L.), and *Fimbristylis miliacea* (L.). Broadleaf weeds were negligible.

Thiobencarb at 1.5 kg ai/ha controlled weeds effectively (biomass

was reduced by 42%), resulting in yield (5.4 t/ha) significantly higher than that of the nonweeded control (3.1 t/ha). Thiobencarb with one hand weeding yielded 5.8 t/ha, two hand weedings yielded 6.2 t/ha, and the weed-free check, 6.0 t/ha. Next were 1 kg 2, 4-D EE/ha and 1.5 kg butachlor granules/ha.

Butachlor EN and Anilofos EC were not effective, probably because rain followed treatment. In cost-benefit ratio, 2 hand weedings gave an extra return of \$291; thiobencarb, \$234; and thiobencarb with one hand weeding, \$250, over the nonweeded control. Two hand weedings at the prevailing labor wage (\$0.84/d) was cheaper than the most promising herbicides, but labor availability is a limitation. □

Effect of herbicides on weed control in transplanted rice. Pantnagar, India, 1984.

Treatment	Concentration ^a (%)	Dose (k/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Weed dry weight at harvest (g/m ²)
Hand weeding twice	—	—	6.2	0
Weed-free check	—	—	6.0	0
Thiobencarb + one weeding	—	—	5.8	42
Thiobencarb	10 G	1.5	5.4	164
Thiobencarb	10 G	1.0	4.2	229
2,4-D EE	4G	1.0	4.7	150
2,4-D EE	4G	0.8	3.9	211
Butachlor	5G	1.5	4.6	266
Butachlor	5G	1.0	3.7	282
Pendimethalin	5G	1.5	4.1	265
Pendimethalin	5G	1.0	3.6	254
Oxyfluorfen	0.35 G	0.15	4.1	242
Oxyfluorfen	0.35 G	0.1	3.2	287
Anilofos ^b	30 EC	0.4	3.7	263
Anilofos ^b	30 EC	0.3	2.5	298
Butachlor ^b	50 EN	1.5	3.1	295
Butachlor ^b	50 EN	1.0	3.1	260
Nonweeded control	—	—	3.1	397
LSD 5%			2.0	

^aG = granule, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, EN = emulsion. ^bRain followed spraying.

Weed species occurring in rice seedling nurseries in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

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We surveyed the weeds in farmers' rice seedling nurseries in Barangay Bantug, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in the 1985 wet and 1986 dry seasons.

In the wet season, 17 species belonging to 13 genera and 7 families were recorded in 17 seedling nurseries; grasses and sedges accounted for 70.6% of the species (see table). In the dry season, nine species belonging to six genera and two families (five species of Poaceae, and four of Cyperaceae) were recorded in three seedling nurseries.

The most commonly occurring species in both seasons were *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *Paspalum distichum*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Scirpus supinus*, *Echinochloa*

Weed species recorded in rice seedling nurseries in Guiramba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1985-86 wet and dry seasons.

Weed species	Family	Wet season, 1985 (17) ^a	Dry season, 1986 (3) ^a
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	+	—
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	+
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	—
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	+
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	+	—
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	+	+
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	+	—
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	+	—
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	+	—
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	+	—
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	+	+
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	Verbenaceae	+	—
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+	+

^aNumber of nurseries surveyed indicated in parentheses; + = present, — = absent.

oryzoides, and *Cyperus difformis*.

Weeds not controlled in the nursery compete with the rice seedlings, resulting in weak seedlings. The weeds

pulled with the rice seedlings also are transplanted. The grassy weeds, in particular, are highly competitive during crop growth. □

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